

M.SC. REMOTE SENSING AND GEOINFORMATICS

LAB ROTATIONS – GEOINFORMATICS

LAB ROTATION I

**DESIGN OF MULTI-SCALE SPATIO-TEMPORAL DATABASE
INFRASTRUCTURE FOR INSPIRE-COMPLIANT WATER
MONITORING**

**OKAN TURHAN
2603348**

JUNE 2026

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Student:	Okan Turhan
Institution:	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)
Program:	M.Sc. Remote Sensing and Geoinformatics
Supervisor:	Prof. Dr. Martin Breunig
Research Assistants:	Paul Kuper, Ruiqi Liu
Lab Rotation I	Design of Multi-Scale Spatio-Temporal Database Infrastructure for INSPIRE-Compliant Water Monitoring.

ABSTRACT

The European Water Framework Directive obliges Member States to monitor every water body against ecological, chemical and quantitative criteria, while the INSPIRE Directive obliges them to share the resulting data in interoperable form. Meeting both obligations in practice requires bringing together remote-sensing imagery, in-situ station records, vector networks and documentary reports. These sources differ in format, in spatial reference system, in temporal cadence and in spatial resolution, yet they must be managed as one queryable whole. This report sets out the design of a database infrastructure that does so for the Karlsruhe region over the period 2005–2025. The design centers on a four-schema architecture in PostgreSQL with PostGIS. A base schema holds the stable geographic substrate, and an rs schema catalogues remote-sensing data and references their out-of-database raster payload. An in-situ schema holds station observations in long form, while a metadata schema carries the ISO 19115 records, the lineage and a pre-computed daily temporal backbone that is referenced by every observation and every acquisition. Spatial reference systems are reconciled once at ingestion against a single storage SRS, ETRS89/UTM zone 32N. Bitemporality, which records both the real-world validity period (valid time) and the database record period (transaction time) of each fact, is applied where the data are routinely revised. INSPIRE conformance is built into the structure of the schema rather than wrapped around it. The architecture is the conceptual and logical specification under which the implementation work of Lab Rotation II will proceed.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	i
ABSTRACT	ii
TABLE OF CONTENTS	iii
LIST OF FIGURES	iv
ABBREVIATIONS	v
1 INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1 Motivation and Problem Statement	1
1.2 Research Objectives.....	2
1.3 Study Area.....	2
2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND AND LITERATURE REVIEW.....	4
2.1 Spatio-Temporal Databases: General Concepts	4
2.2 Spatial Reference Systems	5
2.3 INSPIRE Directive and Spatial Data Infrastructure.....	5
2.4 Water Monitoring Frameworks in Europe	6
3 DATA SOURCE INVESTIGATION.....	8
3.1 Overview and Classification.....	8
3.2 Remote Sensing / Raster Sources	8
3.2.1 Sentinel-2 MSI.....	8
3.2.2 Sentinel-1 SAR.....	9
3.2.3 The Landsat archive.....	9
3.2.4 Digital elevation models	9
3.3 In-Situ and Vector Sources.....	9
3.3.1 Groundwater monitoring.....	9
3.3.2 Surface-water monitoring	10
3.3.3 Meteorological data.....	10
3.3.4 Vector data.....	10
3.4 Documentary Sources	10
4 REQUIREMENTS AND DESIGN CHALLENGES.....	12
4.1 Heterogeneity Challenges	12
4.1.1 Format Heterogeneity	12
4.1.2 Spatial Reference System Heterogeneity.....	12
4.1.3 Temporal Heterogeneity	12
4.1.4 Scale and Resolution Heterogeneity.....	12
4.2 INSPIRE and Functional Requirements.....	13
4.3 Summary of Design Decisions	13
5 CONCEPTUAL AND LOGICAL DATABASE DESIGN	14
5.1 Design Principles.....	14
5.2 Conceptual Data Model.....	14
5.3 Logical Schema (Four-Schema Architecture)	16
5.4 Spatial Reference System Strategy	18
5.5 Temporal Design Strategy.....	18
6 DISCUSSION.....	20
7 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK.....	24
REFERENCES.....	25

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Study Area (Karlsruhe Region)	3
Figure 2. Taxonomy of Water Monitoring Data Sources by Category.	8
Figure 3. Logical Schema of the Four-Schema Database Architecture.	17

ABBREVIATIONS

<p>ALKIS: Amtliches Liegenschaftskataster-Informationssystem (German Official Cadastral Information System)</p> <p>ATKIS: Amtliches Topographisch-Kartographisches Informationssystem (German Official Topographic-Cartographic Information System)</p> <p>ATOM: Atom Syndication Format</p> <p>CEST: Central European Summer Time</p> <p>CET: Central European Time</p> <p>CORINE: Coordination of Information on the Environment</p> <p>CRS: Coordinate Reference System</p> <p>CSV: Comma-Separated Values</p> <p>CSW: Catalogue Service for the Web</p> <p>DEM: Digital Elevation Model</p> <p>DGM: Digitales Geländemodell / digital terrain model</p> <p>DHDN: Deutsches Hauptdreiecksnetz</p> <p>DWD: Deutscher Wetterdienst (German Meteorological Service)</p> <p>EPSG: European Petroleum Survey Group</p> <p>ETL: Extract, Transform, Load</p> <p>ETM+: Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus</p> <p>ETRS89: European Terrestrial Reference System 1989</p> <p>EU: European Union</p> <p>FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable</p> <p>GDAL: Geospatial Data Abstraction Library</p> <p>GDI-DE: Geodateninfrastruktur Deutschland (German Spatial Data Infrastructure)</p> <p>GiST: Generalized Search Tree</p> <p>GIS: Geographic Information System</p> <p>GML: Geography Markup Language</p> <p>GRIB: Gridded Binary</p> <p>INSPIRE: Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community</p> <p>ISO: International Organization for Standardization</p>	<p>JSON: JavaScript Object Notation</p> <p>KIT: Karlsruher Institut für Technologie (Karlsruhe Institute of Technology)</p> <p>L1C: Sentinel-2 Level-1C product</p> <p>L2A: Sentinel-2 Level-2A product</p> <p>LiDAR: Light Detection and Ranging</p> <p>LUBW: Landesanstalt für Umwelt Baden-Württemberg (State Agency for the Environment, Baden-Württemberg)</p> <p>MSI: Multi-Spectral Instrument</p> <p>NDWI: Normalized Difference Water Index</p> <p>NetCDF: Network Common Data Form</p> <p>OGC: Open Geospatial Consortium</p> <p>PDF: Portable Document Format</p> <p>PostGIS: Spatial extension for PostgreSQL</p> <p>REST: Representational State Transfer</p> <p>SAFE: Standard Archive Format for Europe</p> <p>SAR: Synthetic Aperture Radar</p> <p>SLC: Scan Line Corrector</p> <p>SQL: Structured Query Language</p> <p>SRS: Spatial Reference System</p> <p>SRTM: Shuttle Radar Topography Mission</p> <p>SWIR: Short-Wave Infrared</p> <p>TM: Thematic Mapper</p> <p>UTC: Coordinated Universal Time</p> <p>UTM: Universal Transverse Mercator</p> <p>VH: Vertical-Horizontal polarization</p> <p>VV: Vertical-Vertical polarization</p> <p>WaterML: Water Markup Language</p> <p>WCS: Web Coverage Service</p> <p>WFD: Water Framework Directive</p> <p>WFS: Web Feature Service</p> <p>WGS84: World Geodetic System 1984</p> <p>WMS: Web Map Service</p> <p>WSV: Wasserstraßen- und Schifffahrtsverwaltung (German Federal Waterways and Shipping Administration)</p> <p>XML: Extensible Markup Language</p>
--	--

1 INTRODUCTION

Under the WFD (Directive 2000/60/EC), Article 8 requires Member States to establish coherent and comprehensive monitoring programmes within each river basin district to provide an overview of water status. The resulting data feed the status assessment defined in Annex V, under which surface water bodies are classified by ecological status into one of five classes (high, good, moderate, poor, bad) and by chemical status as good or failing to achieve good, while groundwater bodies are classified as good or poor in both quantitative and chemical status. The vision of the Directive is therefore to create a robust, interoperable and transparent framework for assessing ecological, chemical and quantitative aspects of water bodies, identifying pressures, enhancing cross-border cooperation, and guiding policy measures to protect aquatic ecosystems and human health.

The INSPIRE Directive (2007/2/EC) establishes a unified spatial data infrastructure across the European Union to ensure that environmental information is interoperable, accessible, and shared seamlessly among public authorities, researchers, and decision-makers. Its core mission is to standardize geospatial datasets, such as hydrography, land cover, monitoring networks, transport, and administrative boundaries, through common metadata rules, harmonized data models, and web-based services like WMS, WFS, and WCS. By enabling consistent, comparable, and cross-border spatial information, INSPIRE supports evidence-based environmental policy-making and facilitates EU-wide initiatives that rely on coherent geodata, including water management, climate analysis, biodiversity protection, and disaster risk assessment.

Remote sensing and database technologies are essential for reliable and continuous monitoring of water bodies, and it is precisely in alignment with the principles of the Water Framework Directive (WFD) and the INSPIRE Directive that this project adopts a two-phase lab rotation structure. Drawing inspiration from WFD's requirements for coherent, long-term, basin-wide water monitoring and INSPIRE's vision for interoperable, standardized environmental data infrastructures, the project aims to develop a comprehensive multi-scale spatio-temporal information system for the Karlsruhe region (Figure 1). The first lab rotation focuses on the design of the database infrastructure, investigating the heterogeneous data sources available for water monitoring, analyzing the specific requirements and challenges arising from different data formats, spatial reference systems, temporal resolutions, and data types (including raster imagery, in-situ measurements, and documentary sources such as PDF reports), and developing a conceptual and logical database schema that is INSPIRE-compliant and capable of accommodating multi-scale spatio-temporal data.

1.1 Motivation and Problem Statement

Freshwater ecosystems are declining faster than terrestrial or marine systems, with nearly 80% of the world's population exposed to high levels of threat to water security (Vörösmarty et al. 2010). Monitoring is the only empirical basis for detecting these pressures early enough to act on them (Behmel et al. 2016).

The EU Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC) obliges Member States to assess every water body against ecological and chemical status criteria and to renew River Basin Management Plans every six years, generating an unprecedented volume of monitoring data that the Directive itself was never designed to store or curate (Hering et al. 2010; Voulvoulis, Arpon, and Giakoumis 2017).

In practice, WFD-relevant data sit in siloed archives maintained by different agencies, each using incompatible formats, spatial references and vocabularies, and mixing sub-hourly sensor streams with monthly grab samples and annual biological surveys, a fragmentation that makes cross-source analysis slow, expensive and error-prone (Horsburgh et al. 2009; Plana et al. 2019).

Turning compliance data into actionable knowledge requires a common data model and FAIR-aligned (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) access services (Wilkinson et al. 2016). This

work addresses that gap by designing an integrated database infrastructure that harmonizes heterogeneous WFD monitoring data for reuse across assessment, reporting and research.

1.2 Research Objectives

The principal aim of this study is to design, at both the conceptual and the logical level, an integrated database infrastructure that satisfies the interoperability principles laid down by Directive 2007/2/EC (INSPIRE), supports multi-scale representations, and is capable of answering spatio-temporal queries in a coherent manner. Beyond mandating that Member States organize their environmental geospatial holdings into a shared infrastructure, INSPIRE establishes a layered regulatory regime covering metadata, data specifications, network services, data and service sharing, and monitoring obligations (Craglia and Annoni 2007; European Parliament and Council 2007). The architecture proposed here is intended to operate within this regime while moving beyond a purely static "snapshot" view of geographic reality. To that end, the design follows Peuquet's (1994) triadic conceptualization, in which the dimensions of what, where, and when are treated as equal first-class citizens of the data model rather than appended to one another after the fact.

The historical reliance of geographic databases on time-frozen representations and the limitations this place on the analysis of long-running environmental and anthropogenic processes have been examined at length by Langran (1989) and Peuquet (1994). Worboys (1994) extended these arguments by formulating a spatio-bitemporal framework that explicitly couples valid time with transaction time, thereby providing a formal substrate that has shaped subsequent generations of temporal GIS research. The infrastructure outlined in this thesis builds on that theoretical lineage and joins it to the operational requirements set by INSPIRE, with the intention of producing a system that is at once theoretically defensible and regulatorily compliant.

1.3 Study Area

The geographical scope of this study is the Karlsruhe region, situated in the federal state of Baden-Württemberg in south-western Germany. The study area is defined by a rectangular extent of approximately 740 km² centered on the city of Karlsruhe (Figure 1), crossed from south to north by the Rhine and extending eastwards to the foothills of the northern Black Forest.

Although the database design developed in this work is regionally instantiated for Karlsruhe, the schema itself is constructed in a generic, location-agnostic manner so that the architecture remains transferable to other Baden-Württemberg districts and, more broadly, to any INSPIRE-conformant administrative unit.

The temporal envelope considered in this study spans the two decades from 2005 to 2025. The lower bound was deliberately placed two years prior to the entry into force of Directive 2007/2/EC, so that the dataset captures both the pre-INSPIRE state of regional geodata holdings and the transformation triggered by the Directive's implementing rules between 2008 and 2014.

Within these geographical and temporal boundaries, the work is scoped to the conceptual and logical levels of database design; physical realization, including ingestion pipelines, indexing strategy and empirical performance evaluation, is reserved for Lab Rotation II. Several further restrictions delimit the present scope. The schema is developed for two- and two-and-a-half-dimensional vector geometry, with elevation treated as an attribute; full three-dimensional and CityGML-style modelling lies outside this work. Streaming and near-real-time sensor data are not treated as primary inputs, since the design assumes update cycles ranging from daily to multi-annual, which corresponds to the cadence of the WFD and INSPIRE themes considered. Privately held or licensed datasets are noted in the inventory only where they materially shape the public data landscape and are not integrated into the schema, and the legal-policy interpretation of INSPIRE compliance is treated only insofar as it constrains technical decisions.

Within these geographical boundaries, the regional data landscape is exceptionally rich. The LUBW groundwater monitoring network alone comprises 61 quality stations (Grundwassergüte) and 110 quantity stations (Grundwassermenge) inside the study extent, reflecting Karlsruhe's location on the Upper Rhine Graben aquifer. The left bank of the Rhine, which lies in the federal state of Rheinland-Pfalz, falls outside the administrative jurisdiction of Baden-Württemberg and is therefore excluded from the present work, even where it appears within the rectangular extent for geographical context.

Figure 1. Study Area (Karlsruhe Region)

The design of an integrated spatio-temporal database for water monitoring draws on four bodies of knowledge that intersect only partially in the existing literature: the modelling of space and time in database systems, the formalism of spatial reference systems, the regulatory architecture of the INSPIRE Directive, and the monitoring obligations of European water policy.

2.1 Spatio-Temporal Databases: General Concepts

A spatial database extends the conventional relational model with the data types, operators and indexing mechanisms that allow geometric objects—points, lines, polygons and rasters—to be stored, queried and analyzed within the database engine itself rather than in an external geographic information system. A temporal database, by contrast, is concerned with the explicit representation of time, enabling a system to record not only the current state of an entity but also the history of its states and the evolution of its description. A spatio-temporal database unifies these two concerns: it manages objects that possess a geometry, a set of thematic attributes and a temporal extent, and it supports queries that constrain all three dimensions simultaneously. The conceptual necessity of treating these dimensions jointly was articulated early by Langran (1989) and given its most influential formulation by Peuquet (1994), whose triad of what, where and when remains the standard reference frame for spatio-temporal modelling.

Three families of data model are commonly distinguished. The snapshot model represents reality as a sequence of complete, time-stamped layers; it is simple to implement but stores large volumes of redundant data and cannot easily express the identity of an object through change. The event- or change-based model records only the differences between successive states, which is storage-efficient and well suited to processes with infrequent updates, but reconstructing the state at an arbitrary instant requires accumulating those changes. The object-relational model, which underlies the architecture proposed in this work, treats each real-world entity as a persistent object whose geometry and attributes carry their own temporal stamps, allowing both the history of an object and the relationships between objects to be queried directly.

The treatment of time itself requires several distinctions that are central to the later design. Valid time denotes the period during which a fact is true in the modelled reality; transaction time denotes the period during which a fact is stored in the database; and decision time denotes when a decision recorded by the fact was taken. A database that supports both valid and transaction time is termed bitemporal, and the bitemporal framework formalized by Worboys (1994) is particularly relevant here because environmental monitoring data are routinely revised, a measurement may be corrected, a water-body boundary re-delineated, or a code list updated long after the observation was originally recorded. Temporal granularity, the resolution at which time is recorded, ranging from sub-hourly sensor readings to annual reporting cycles, and the distinction between regularly sampled time series and irregular, event-driven observations are likewise decisive for harmonization. Finally, qualitative reasoning over temporal relations is captured by Allen's interval algebra (Allen 1983), whose thirteen mutually exclusive relations between time intervals provide a vocabulary for expressing and validating temporal constraints during data integration.

These concepts are operationalized in this project through the PostgreSQL object-relational database system and its PostGIS extension. PostGIS adds OGC-compliant geometry and geography types, raster support, and spatial indexing based on GiST R-tree variants, while PostgreSQL contributes native temporal types, range types and table partitioning. Together they provide a standards-based, open-source platform on which spatial and temporal functionality can be combined without recourse to proprietary software, and on which the conceptual model developed in later sections can be physically realized.

2.2 Spatial Reference Systems

A spatial reference system (SRS), or coordinate reference system (CRS), is the formal specification that gives numerical coordinates an unambiguous meaning on the surface of the Earth. It combines a datum, a model of the Earth's shape and its orientation in space, with a coordinate system and, in the case of projected systems, a map projection. Geodetic (geographic) reference systems express position as latitude and longitude on the ellipsoid, whereas projected reference systems transform those positions onto a plane so that distances, areas and angles can be measured in linear units. Each system in common use is catalogued by a numeric identifier in the EPSG Geodetic Parameter Dataset, and these EPSG codes provide the practical means by which software identifies and transforms between reference systems.

For a study situated in Germany, several reference systems are of immediate relevance. ETRS89, realized in practice through the UTM projection for zone 32N (EPSG:25832), is the official reference system for Baden-Württemberg and for most contemporary INSPIRE-conformant datasets.

The coexistence of these systems is the source of a recurrent integration problem. Combining datasets that use different reference systems requires reprojection, and reprojection is not error-free: datum transformations rely on empirically derived parameters, and the choice of transformation method introduces positional discrepancies that, although typically small, are not negligible when point observations must be matched to raster pixels of only a few meters' extent. Reprojecting data repeatedly, or applying inconsistent transformations across sources, accumulates error and undermines the spatial joins on which multi-source analysis depends. The design consequence drawn in this work is that a single storage reference system is adopted for the database, that all incoming data are transformed to it once through documented transformation paths, and that reprojection to other systems is performed on the fly only at the point of delivery, so that the authoritative stored geometry is never degraded by successive transformations.

2.3 INSPIRE Directive and Spatial Data Infrastructure

Before INSPIRE, environmental policy across the European Union depended on data that no two Member States held in the same way. Authorities in Germany described their water bodies in German, French agencies in French; one distributed its river network as Shapefile in ETRS89, another as GML in a national legacy datum; one used the term “Gewässer”, another “cours d'eau”, for the same hydrological reality. Cross-border environmental questions, the state of a shared river basin, the trajectory of nitrate concentrations across the Rhine corridor, could be asked, but could not be answered without a disproportionate effort of translation, reprojection and reformatting performed anew for each study. Directive 2007/2/EC, establishing the Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community (INSPIRE), is the legal response to this fragmentation. Rather than building a central European database, the Directive obliges Member States to document and share the spatial data they already hold according to a common set of rules, producing a federated infrastructure assembled from harmonized national components (European Parliament and Council 2007). Craglia and Annoni (2007) characterise the design as deliberately incremental: interoperability is achieved through agreed specifications rather than through centralization, so that existing national investments are preserved rather than replaced.

The Directive operationalizes this principle through five interdependent components. *Metadata* obliges every dataset and service to carry a standardized description, title, abstract, spatial and temporal extent, reference system, lineage, point of contact-encoded under ISO 19115 and ISO 19139, without which a dataset is effectively invisible to the infrastructure. *Data specifications* define harmonized conceptual models for thirty-four spatial data themes organized in three annexes; a Member State retains its national data but must be able to deliver it as the INSPIRE-conformant model when requested. The themes most relevant to water monitoring are *Hydrography* in Annex I, *Environmental Monitoring*

Facilities in Annex III, and *Administrative Units, Elevation, Ortho imagery* and *Land Cover* distributed across the three annexes. *Network services* prescribe the means of access through the OGC standards: discovery services (CSW) for finding data, view services (WMS) for visualizing it, download services (WFS for vector, WCS for raster, ATOM feeds for pre-packaged datasets) for retrieving it, and transformation services for reprojection and schema mediation. The remaining components govern *data and service sharing* between authorities, and *monitoring and reporting* of national implementation progress to the European Commission.

In Germany, INSPIRE is coordinated through the Geodateninfrastruktur Deutschland (GDI-DE), which aligns federal, Land and municipal authorities under a common technical regime, while the operational publication of Baden-Württemberg's geodata is handled by the Landesamt für Geoinformation und Landentwicklung through the Geoportal Baden-Württemberg. The relationship between INSPIRE and the Water Framework Directive is one of complementary mandates: WFD prescribes *what* must be monitored and reported, INSPIRE prescribes *how* the resulting data must be structured and shared, and the integrated monitoring infrastructure envisaged in this work necessarily addresses both. For the design developed in the following sections, INSPIRE is significant in three concrete respects. It defines the target conceptual models with which the database schema must align if the system is to be interoperable. It requires that ISO 19115 metadata and explicit lineage be carried alongside every dataset, so that provenance and discoverability are structural rather than retrofitted. And it constrains the choice of code lists, identifier schemes and coordinate reference systems toward those registered in the INSPIRE registry. These requirements are treated here not as an external compliance exercise but as design inputs that shape the conceptual and logical model from the outset.

2.4 Water Monitoring Frameworks in Europe

While INSPIRE governs how spatial data are structured and shared, it is the EU Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC) that defines what water-related data must be collected and why (European Commission 2012). Adopted in 2000, the WFD established an integrated, river-basin-based regime under which all European water bodies must achieve "good status", a composite assessment combining ecological status (judged by biological quality elements such as fish, benthic invertebrates and macrophytes, with supporting hydromorphological and physico-chemical parameters), chemical status (compliance with environmental quality standards for priority substances such as heavy metals and pesticides), and, for groundwater, quantitative status. Article 8 establishes the monitoring obligation, and the resulting evidence is consolidated every six years into River Basin Management Plans, published in 2009, 2015 and 2021, with the next due in 2027. The original 2015 target was met by fewer than half of monitored water bodies, and the extended 2027 deadline coincides with the upper bound of this study's temporal window. Two decades of implementation have documented uneven progress and a heavy reporting burden (Hering et al. 2010; Voulvoulis et al. 2017), and it is this burden of storing, curating and comparing heterogeneous monitoring data that motivates the database infrastructure designed in this work.

The WFD distinguishes three monitoring programmes whose distinction shapes the temporal structure of the data. Surveillance monitoring provides a broad, long-term overview; operational monitoring is more frequent and targeted at water bodies at risk; and investigative monitoring is undertaken ad hoc to determine the causes of failure. These programmes generate data at very different cadences, from continuously logging gauging stations to annual biological surveys, and the comparability of their indicators across water bodies depends on shared definitions and consistent measurement standards (Behmel et al. 2016). A database supporting WFD reporting must therefore accommodate variable sampling regimes rather than assume a single one.

At the regional scale, water monitoring in Baden-Württemberg is the responsibility of the Landesanstalt für Umwelt Baden-Württemberg (LUBW), which operates the state's groundwater and surface-water networks. Surface-water levels and discharge along the Rhine are additionally available

through the federal Pegelonline service, and meteorological variables through the Deutscher Wetterdienst. These institutions constitute the empirical data landscape for the Karlsruhe region; their holdings are examined in Section 1.3.

3 DATA SOURCE INVESTIGATION

A database can be designed well only against an accurate picture of the data it must hold. This section investigates the data sources available for water monitoring in the Karlsruhe region, characterizing each one in terms of its format, reference system and the specific processing it demands, and connecting those properties to the design choices developed in Section 1.5. The full inventory of sources, with their providers, formats, resolutions and access routes, is summarized across the subsections that follow; the text concentrates on the characteristics that have direct architectural consequences.

3.1 Overview and Classification

The data relevant to multi-scale spatio-temporal water monitoring divide into four categories whose structural differences are the origin of nearly every design problem addressed in this report. *Remote-sensing* data are raster coverages: regular grids of pixels, spatially continuous but temporally intermittent, and large in volume. *In-situ* data are the opposite, point geometries that are spatially sparse but temporally dense, recording one or a few locations continuously for years. *Vector* data are neither sampled nor gridded but delineated, discrete lines and polygons representing river networks, catchments and administrative units, valuable less for their attributes than for the topology that connects them. *Documentary* data are unstructured, holding in narrative and tabular PDF the official assessment results that no structured feed reproduces. A database serving all four must reconcile coverages that are continuous in space against series that are continuous in time, and structured numerical observations against unstructured text; that reconciliation is the central design problem of this work (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Taxonomy of Water Monitoring Data Sources by Category.

3.2 Remote Sensing / Raster Sources

Four product families cover the 2005–2025 study period: three provide synoptic, repeated observation of the study area, while digital elevation models provide a largely static topographic baseline.

3.2.1 Sentinel-2 MSI

When both satellites are merged, this data provides multispectral optical images in thirteen bands with a five-day revisit. For water monitoring its decisive channels are the green and near-infrared bands

behind the Normalized Difference Water Index (McFeeters 1996), and the short-wave infrared bands behind the Modified NDWI (Xu 2006), which separates open water from built-up land far more reliably because water absorbs SWIR almost entirely. Imagery is delivered as 100×100 km tiles in SAFE format, each projected into its local UTM zone. Level-2A products provide atmospherically corrected surface reflectance with a Scene Classification Layer flagging cloud, shadow and water; Level-1C provides only top-of-atmosphere values. In the cloudy climate of south-western Germany, cloud and cloud-shadow pixels must be masked before any index is computed, and where only Level-1C is available, atmospheric correction must precede any comparison between dates.

3.2.2 Sentinel-1 SAR

This C-band synthetic-aperture radar is the guarantee of observations when Sentinel-2 fails, because it actively transmits its own microwave pulses and is therefore unaffected by cloud cover or darkness. Its value for water mapping rests on a physical effect: a calm water surface acts as a mirror, reflecting the radar pulse away from the sensor, so that open water appears almost black against a brighter land background. The Interferometric Wide-swath product used here is delivered at roughly 5×20 m in VV and VH polarization, but it cannot be used as delivered; it requires an ordered preprocessing chain of orbit-file application, radiometric calibration, speckle filtering, and Range-Doppler terrain correction, without which the imagery can neither be interpreted nor co-registered with other layers.

3.2.3 The Landsat archive

Since Sentinel-2 only started in 2015, the years 2005–2014 are covered by Landsat 5 TM (acquiring until 2011) and Landsat 7 ETM+, with Landsat 8 continuing from 2013 and Landsat 9 from 2021. This extends the optical record backward. All are available as Collection 2 Level-2 surface-reflectance products at 30 m resolution. Two complications attach to this source. Landsat 7, since the failure of its Scan Line Corrector in 2003, produces imagery with systematic wedge-shaped gaps that remove roughly a fifth of every scene, so that ETM+ data must be gap-filled or used only in composites. And combining Landsat with Sentinel-2 in a continuous series requires harmonizing both spatial resolution (30 m against 10–20 m) and slightly different spectral band definitions, without which an apparent change in a water index could reflect the instrument rather than the ground.

3.2.4 Digital elevation models

Topography drives hydrological reasoning. Flow direction, flow accumulation and catchment delineation are derived from a digital elevation model rather than directly observed, and the resolution of the model determines which features are resolvable at all. Three sources span an order of magnitude: the Copernicus DEM at 30 m globally and 10 m over Europe, the older SRTM at 30–90 m, and the LiDAR-derived model published for Baden-Württemberg at 1 m. Before hydrological use they require void filling, hydrological conditioning to remove spurious sinks, and a deliberate resampling strategy when models of differing resolution are combined.

3.3 In-Situ and Vector Sources

In-situ stations are spatially sparse but temporally dense, and they carry the high-accuracy measurements that anchor remote-sensing validation and constitute the legal evidence of water status.

3.3.1 Groundwater monitoring

Groundwater is not a secondary concern in this study area. Karlsruhe sits on the Upper Rhine Graben aquifer, one of the largest groundwater bodies in central Europe, and the regional monitoring network reflects that significance. The LUBW operates the regional network through two complementary monitoring programmes: a quality network (Grundwassergüte) recording chemical parameters such as nitrate, electrical conductivity, temperature and trace contaminants, and a quantity

network (Grundwassermenge) recording groundwater level and source discharge. Within the Karlsruhe study area alone, 61 quality stations have generated approximately 110,000 individual measurements since 2005, while 110 quantity stations are operated for level monitoring. Data are distributed as CSV and XML. The characteristic difficulty is internal heterogeneity: within a single parameter, some stations are read by continuous loggers at hourly intervals while others are measured manually at monthly intervals; periods of record begin and end at different dates; stations are taken out of service; and reported units are not always uniform. A schema for these data cannot assume a fixed sampling cadence and must treat the measurement interval as itself a property of the observation.

3.3.2 Surface-water monitoring

Surface-water monitoring covers discharge, water level and water-quality parameters along the Rhine and its tributaries. The LUBW networks are complemented by Pegelonline, the federal Wasserstraßen- und Schifffahrtsverwaltung service that publishes near-real-time level and discharge for the navigable Rhine. Data are available as CSV, as JSON over a REST interface, and as WaterML 2.0, the OGC standard for hydrological time series, which is directly relevant to interoperability. Gauge readings during flood peaks may be provisional or out of calibrated range and so carry lower reliability precisely when they matter most, and station metadata between the regional and federal networks must be reconciled before a gauge can be unambiguously identified.

3.3.3 Meteorological data

The Deutscher Wetterdienst's open Climate Data Center provides meteorological data, which serves as the benchmark for interpreting surface and groundwater behavior. The DWD distributes precipitation, air temperature and evapotranspiration in two distinct forms: as station records and as gridded products interpolated or radar-derived across the area, the latter in GRIB and NetCDF. The design must decide which representation each analysis requires and how the two relate, since a station value and a grid cell are not interchangeable.

3.3.4 Vector data

Vector data supply the discrete geographic framework to which observations are attached. The most important of these is the Gewässernetz Baden-Württemberg, the official hydrological network representing rivers, catchments and lake boundaries. It is available in ETRS89/UTM 32N as Shapefile, GeoPackage, and INSPIRE-conformant GML. Because this layer is a network rather than a set of lines, its usefulness depends entirely on topological consistency: a single undetected gap or misaligned junction breaks the connectivity on which upstream-downstream tracing depends, and connectivity checking is therefore a precondition of use rather than an optional refinement. Administrative and land-cover data complete the context: cadastral and topographic information from ALKIS and ATKIS, and land cover from CORINE Land Cover (available both as vector polygons and as a 100 m raster) and the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service. Land cover is itself a monitored, time-varying quantity, and CORINE's coarse minimum mapping unit must be reconciled with the finer detail of the cadaster wherever the two are used together.

3.4 Documentary Sources

A significant part of the evidence base for water monitoring exists only as text. The LUBW publishes annual monitoring reports; the WFD process produces River Basin Management Plans (Bewirtschaftungspläne) revised on the six-year cycle in 2009, 2015 and 2021; and the ecological and chemical status of individual water bodies is recorded in periodic assessment documents (Zustandsbewertungen). These sources are overwhelmingly PDF, and they matter because they hold what the structured feeds do not: the official status classifications and the interpretive reasoning behind them, in effect the conclusions of the monitoring process. Their incorporation poses problems the numerical sources do not. Tabulated results must be extracted from a layout designed for human reading;

older documents that survive only as scans require optical character recognition; and each document must be described by metadata (author, date, region, parameters addressed) before it can be located. The design decision that follows, developed in Section 1.5.3, is deliberate: the database does not ingest the full text of these documents but references them, holding for each a file path, a summary, a keyword index, a version and the spatial units and time periods it concerns, so that an official assessment can always be retrieved alongside the observations it interprets.

The data investigation of Section 1.3 makes clear that no single property of any one source is the source of difficulty; the difficulty lies in the combination. This section translates that combination into the explicit requirements that the database design of Section 1.5 must satisfy, separating the structural challenges of heterogeneity from the obligations imposed by INSPIRE and from the functional expectations of the system, and summarizing the resulting design choices.

4.1 Heterogeneity Challenges

Four axes of heterogeneity run through the data inventory, and each imposes a distinct architectural requirement on the database.

4.1.1 Format Heterogeneity

The native formats of the source inventory are mutually incompatible at almost every level. Rasters arrive as GeoTIFF, as JPEG 2000 inside SAFE archives, and as NetCDF or GRIB. Vector data are distributed as Shapefile, GeoPackage, GML or GeoJSON. Time series come as CSV, XML, JSON and the OGC WaterML 2.0 standard. Documentary content arrives only as PDF. None of these is suitable as an internal database representation, and the architecture therefore draws a clean boundary at ingestion: every data class is converted, on entry, into a canonical internal form (geometry for vector, raster for gridded coverages, narrow-format tables for time series, file references for documents), and downstream of that boundary only canonical representations exist. The database is not asked to support all input formats; it is asked to enforce one internal representation per data class.

4.1.2 Spatial Reference System Heterogeneity

The same Karlsruhe scene arrives in ETRS89/UTM 32N from regional authorities, in DHDN/Gauß-Krüger from legacy national holdings, in WGS84/UTM from Sentinel and Landsat, and in WGS84 geographic coordinates from many web services. Reprojection between these systems is not error-free, and repeated reprojection increases error. The database must use a single storage SRS, have all incoming data translated to it exactly once using defined transformation routes, and reprojection to other systems for delivery occur on the fly without altering the stored geometry. The reasoning behind the specific SRS choice is developed in Section 1.5.4.

4.1.3 Temporal Heterogeneity

The data are sampled at cadences spanning about five orders of magnitude: sub-hourly gauge readings, five-day Sentinel revisits, monthly groundwater grab samples, annual reports, and the six-yearly River Basin Management Plan cycle. They are recorded against different time references (UTC for satellite acquisitions, CET/CEST for station data) and aggregated to different cut-off conventions. The requirement is that the schema impose no implicit assumption of regularity, that it carries the measurement interval as an explicit property of each observation rather than as a column header, and that it provides a common temporal backbone against which observations of any cadence can be aligned without ad hoc date arithmetic. The design of that backbone is developed in Section 1.5.5.

4.1.4 Scale and Resolution Heterogeneity

Spatial resolution ranges from 1 m LiDAR through 10–20 m Sentinel-2 and 30 m Landsat to the 100 m grid of CORINE Land Cover, with point in-situ stations occupying no resolution at all in the conventional sense. Temporal resolution shows the same dispersion, from hourly logger readings to six-yearly plans. The requirement is that resolution be treated as a recorded attribute of each dataset rather than as an assumption baked into table structures, so that a one-meter raster and a hundred-meter

coverage can coexist in the same schema and a query can select among them by an explicit resolution criterion.

4.2 INSPIRE and Functional Requirements

INSPIRE conformance imposes a set of structural obligations that the schema must meet before any consideration of performance. Metadata for every dataset and service must be captured under ISO 19115 with ISO 19139 encoding, including title, abstract, spatial and temporal extent, reference system, lineage and point of contact. The conceptual classes of the database must align with the INSPIRE data specifications for the themes relevant to water monitoring, principally Hydrography (Annex I) for water bodies and river networks, Environmental Monitoring Facilities (Annex III) for in-situ stations, and the supporting themes of Administrative Units, Elevation, Ortho imagery and Land Cover. Code lists for thematic attributes (water-body category, monitoring purpose, parameter type) must reference the INSPIRE registry rather than carry locally invented values. Lineage must be recorded explicitly so that the path from external source to stored record is fully reproducible. And the schema must be publishable through OGC network services (WMS, WFS, WCS), which means that the geometry, attribute and metadata structures of the database must be expressible in the data models those services expect.

The functional requirements concern what the database must do once these structural conditions are met. It must support spatio-temporal join queries that combine vector, raster and observational data through their shared spatial and temporal anchors, returning results in interactive time for the typical analytical scale of a catchment over a year. It must support multi-scale queries that select datasets by their recorded resolution. It must support bitemporal querying, separating the state of the data as currently believed from the state as believed at any past moment, since environmental monitoring data are revised after the fact. It must accommodate three user profiles whose access patterns differ: researchers performing analytical queries, decision-makers seeking aggregated indicators, and reporting workflows producing the periodic outputs required by WFD compliance. The schema is expected to satisfy these requirements at the conceptual and logical level; the physical realization, including indexing, partitioning and query tuning, is reserved for Lab Rotation II.

4.3 Summary of Design Decisions

The requirements of Sections 1.4.1 and 1.4.2 are not independent, and the design must address them as a coherent set rather than one at a time. The principal decisions can be summarized here. Formats are normalized at ingestion to a canonical internal representation per data class. The storage SRS is fixed as ETRS89/UTM zone 32N (EPSG:25832), with all transformation performed once on entry. Temporal alignment is achieved through a shared backbone of daily time identifiers in a metadata schema, with finer granularity carried as an additional timestamp where needed and coarser cadences bound through validity intervals. Resolution is recorded as an attribute on every dataset rather than encoded in table structure. Raster payload is held as out-of-database files referenced from a catalogue table, while the catalogue itself lives in the database alongside vector and observational data. Documentary content is referenced rather than ingested, with metadata sufficient to locate and contextualize each document. INSPIRE conformance is achieved through structural alignment with the relevant themes and through ISO 19115 metadata held in a dedicated schema.

The design developed in this section answers the central question of this report: how can heterogeneous, multi-temporal and multi-scale water-monitoring data be integrated into a single PostGIS database that is interoperable under INSPIRE and that supports the rapid spatio-temporal queries on which monitoring depends. The answer rests on three commitments that recur through every subsection. First, the database is partitioned by responsibility into four schemas rather than collapsed into a single namespace, so that raster, vector, observational and metadata content can be reasoned about, indexed and evolved independently. Second, the four schemas are bound together by two common references, a spatial backbone in the *base* schema and a temporal backbone in the *metadata* schema, so that integration becomes a matter of joining on shared keys rather than reconciling parallel structures. Third, INSPIRE alignment and multi-resolution support are treated as design inputs from the outset, not as features wrapped around a generic schema after the fact.

5.1 Design Principles

The architecture rests on several interlocking principles, and the relations among them matter as much as the principles taken one by one.

Raster, vector, observational and metadata content differ in volume, in update frequency and in the way they are queried. Combining them in a flat namespace would couple optimization choices that should be made independently, so the database is split into four schemas, *base*, *rs*, *insitu* and *metadata*, each carrying a single semantic responsibility while sharing one physical instance. That separation only helps, however, if the schemas can still be queried together. The architecture provides for this through two shared backbones: every entity with a location refers, directly or transitively, to a stable geometric object in *base*, and every entity with a time refers to a row in the temporal index in *metadata*. Cross-source joins therefore become key matches rather than ad hoc spatial or temporal reconciliations.

INSPIRE alignment is treated as a design input rather than a wrapper. The conceptual model adopts the data themes most relevant to water monitoring (Hydrography, Environmental Monitoring Facilities, Ortho imagery, Elevation, Administrative Units, Land Cover) from the beginning, and ISO 19115 metadata is given its own table rather than scattered as columns across the schemas. Multi-scale support follows the same logic: spatial resolution and temporal granularity are explicit attributes on each dataset, so that a one-meter LiDAR raster and a hundred-meter land-cover layer can coexist in the same schema and be selected against by an explicit criterion.

Two further commitments shape the design less visibly. The schema is built to be extended without restructuring, so that adding a new data source, a new monitored parameter or extending the spatial coverage beyond Karlsruhe is an insert into a catalogue table rather than a change to the schema itself. And the scope is deliberately restricted: this work develops the conceptual and logical levels of design, while physical realization, including ingestion pipelines, indexing strategy and performance tuning, is reserved for Lab Rotation II. The logical model is nevertheless expressed against PostgreSQL with the PostGIS and PostGIS Raster extensions, whose geometry types, GiST spatial indexing, native temporal types and table partitioning the design assumes.

5.2 Conceptual Data Model

The conceptual model describes the entities the database represents and the relationships among them without committing to a particular storage layout. It is built on Peuquet's (1994) triad in which *what* is observed, *where* it is observed and *when* it is observed are treated as equally fundamental: the model carries no entity in which any of the three is implicit.

The geographic substrate of the database is the SpatialUnit: the water bodies, river segments, catchment areas, lake polygons and administrative units to which every other entity ultimately refers. A

SpatialUnit carries a geometry, a unit type drawn from the INSPIRE Hydrography vocabulary, and valid-time and transaction-time intervals, since water-body delineations are themselves revised over the lifetime of the database. MonitoringStation is a specialised entity for the fixed-point locations at which in-situ measurement occurs; it carries a point geometry, a network affiliation (LUBW groundwater, LUBW surface water, Pegelonline, DWD), and the station-level metadata required by the INSPIRE Environmental Monitoring Facilities specification. The decision to model station as a distinct entity rather than as an attribute of observation is deliberate: stations have lifetimes, addresses and provenance independent of any measurement, and a one-to-many relationship from station to observation captures this asymmetry exactly.

Together with MonitoringStation introduced above, the in-situ measurement record is decomposed into three entities rather than collapsed into one. Parameter is the catalogue of measurable quantities (water level, discharge, temperature, electrical conductivity, nitrate, precipitation, evapotranspiration), each with a canonical unit and, where applicable, a mapping to the corresponding INSPIRE code list. Observation is the measured value itself, modelled in narrow rather than wide form: each row records a single value of a single parameter at a single station at a single time, together with a quality flag and the valid-time and transaction-time stamps that make corrections traceable. This long-format decomposition is a substantive modelling choice rather than a stylistic preference. A wide table with one column per parameter would force the schema to commit to a fixed list of parameters at design time and would waste storage on null values for every parameter not measured at a given station; the narrow form absorbs both variable cadence and new parameters through inserts to the Parameter catalogue, requiring no schema change.

Remote-sensing data are modelled along the same separation of catalogue from payload. RasterDataset describes a single acquisition or derived product through scene-level attributes: sensor, product level, acquisition timestamp, footprint geometry, spatial resolution, cloud-cover fraction, and a reference to the temporal backbone. It is light, queryable and indexed. RasterTile references the actual raster payload (held as out-of-database files, see Section 1.5.3), separated from the dataset so that the catalogue can be filtered and joined with vector data without ever touching the heavy raster payload. The relationship is one-to-many: a dataset may comprise one tile or many. The separation is what makes a question like "*which Sentinel-2 acquisitions over the Alb catchment in summer 2018 had less than ten percent cloud cover*" answerable efficiently as an indexed query against the catalogue alone, without touching the raster payload (empirical timings are reserved for Lab Rotation II).

The fourth class of source is modelled through DocumentReference. The database does not ingest the full text of LUBW annual reports, Bewirtschaftungspläne or status assessments; it references them, holding for each a file path, a summary, a keyword index, a version, and many-to-many associations to the spatial units and time periods the document concerns. This treats documents as first-class objects of the monitoring archive without subjecting the database to the problems of unstructured text retrieval.

The temporal backbone is the entity TimeIndex, a pre-computed calendar of dates that every observation and every raster dataset reference through a foreign key. Its purpose is explained in Section 1.5.5; here it suffices to note that its presence at the conceptual level is what permits queries to be expressed in terms of months, seasons or years as joins rather than as repeated extractions of date components. MetadataRecord carries the ISO 19115 metadata for any dataset, regardless of which schema it sits in, so that the INSPIRE discovery layer has a single, uniformly structured place to read from. DataLineage records, for each ingested record, the source, the date of ingestion and the transformations applied, so that the path from external file to stored row is fully reproducible.

Two modelling decisions cut across the entities. The first is bitemporality on the entities most subject to revision (Observation and SpatialUnit geometry), implemented as paired valid-time and transaction-time intervals after Worboys (1994), so that the historical record reflects both how reality was and how the database represented it at any past moment. The second is the explicit use of stereotypes for spatial attributes (*<<geometry>>* with an SRS reference) and temporal attributes (*<<valid time>>*,

<<*transaction time*>>, <<*time_id*>>) on every relevant entity, both for conceptual clarity and to make INSPIRE alignment visible at the level of the model.

5.3 Logical Schema (Four-Schema Architecture)

The conceptual model is realized in PostgreSQL as four schemas, each carrying a single semantic responsibility. The discussion here states the structure and the reasoning; the logical schema in Figure 3 shows which conceptual entity is realized in which physical table.

The base schema holds the stable geographic substrate. Its principal table, *base.spatial_unit*, stores water bodies, river segments, catchment areas, lake polygons and administrative units, each with a PostGIS geometry column constrained to the storage SRS, a unit-type column drawn from the INSPIRE Hydrography code list, and bitemporal interval columns recording when the delineation was valid in reality and when it was recorded in the database. Its second table, *base.monitoring_station*, holds the point geometries of LUBW, Pegelonline and DWD stations together with the network affiliation and the station metadata required by INSPIRE Environmental Monitoring Facilities. Both tables expose stable surrogate identifiers that the other three schemas reference through foreign keys; the base schema is, in this sense, the spatial anchor of the database.

The *rs* schema holds the remote-sensing catalogue and the references to its payload. *rs.rs_dataset* stores one row per acquisition or derived product: sensor identifier, product level (L1C, L2A, Collection-2 Level-2), acquisition timestamp, footprint geometry constrained to the storage SRS, spatial resolution, cloud-cover fraction, and a *time_id* foreign key to *metadata.time_index*. *rs.rs_tile* realises the hybrid raster strategy adopted in this work: rather than load potentially terabytes of imagery into the database as in-database PostGIS raster, the table holds an out-of-database raster reference (file path, format, extent, band count) to GeoTIFF files held on the filesystem, registered through PostGIS Raster's *out_db* mechanism so that the rasters remain queryable as if they were stored in the database. The reasoning is operational. A twenty-year multi-resolution archive ranging from one-metre LiDAR to thirty-metre Landsat would inflate the database to a size that compromises routine backup, replication and maintenance; full in-database storage of the payload would also remove the rasters from direct use by GDAL-based tooling. A catalogue-plus-reference approach keeps the database light, preserves the rasters as first-class files for external processing, and still supports SQL-level discovery, footprint joins with vector data, and on-the-fly raster operations through the *out_db* interface.

The *insitu* schema holds the observational record. *insitu.parameter* is the catalogue of measurable quantities, each row carrying a parameter type, a canonical unit, and, where applicable, a reference to the corresponding INSPIRE code list. *insitu.observation* is the central long-format table: one row per measured value, with foreign keys to *insitu.parameter* (what), *base.monitoring_station* (where) and *metadata.time_index* (when), together with the observed value, the unit at acquisition, a quality flag, an optional sub-daily *obs_timestamp* for finer-than-daily measurements, and the valid-time and transaction-time interval columns that make the record bitemporal. The narrow structure is what makes it possible to store, in a single table and without schema change, the hourly groundwater levels of one station alongside the monthly nitrate concentrations of another.

The metadata schema is the connective tissue of the database. *metadata.time_index* is the temporal backbone, a daily calendar populated once at database initialisation through a *generate_series* over the study period 2005–2025, carrying a surrogate *time_id* primary key, the date itself, and the derived columns year, month, day, quarter, season, week, *iso_week* and *day_of_year*. *metadata.metadata_record* holds ISO 19115 metadata for each dataset, regardless of which schema it sits in. *metadata.data_lineage* records the provenance of each ingested record: source, date of ingestion, transformations applied (including the specific SRS transformation parameters from Section 1.5.4), and software version. *metadata.document_reference* realises the documentary-source model: one row per referenced PDF, with file path, summary, keyword index, version and many-to-many associations to the spatial units and time periods the document concerns.

The decisive structural consequence of this layout, and the answer to how four schemas constitute one database rather than four disconnected ones, is that the schemas are not parallel. They are bound through two shared keys: every entity with a location refers through a foreign key into base, and every entity with a time refers through a foreign key into metadata.time_index. A query that asks, for instance, "the in-situ nitrate concentrations and the closest Sentinel-2 NDWI values for water bodies in the Alb catchment in the summer of 2018" expresses itself as a single SQL statement that joins insitu.observation to base.spatial_unit on geometry, to insitu.parameter on parameter type, and to metadata.time_index on date, while joining rs.rs_dataset to the same spatial_unit on footprint and to the same time_index on date. The four schemas are conceptually distinct and physically separable, but they are queried as one.

Figure 3. Logical Schema of the Four-Schema Database Architecture.

5.4 Spatial Reference System Strategy

The data sources of Section 1.3 arrive in at least four reference systems: ETRS89/UTM zone 32N for native regional data, the legacy DHDN with Gauß-Krüger for older holdings, WGS84/UTM zone 32N for Sentinel and Landsat imagery, and WGS84 geographic coordinates for many web services. The design must decide how, where and when these are reconciled, and the choice adopted in this work is to fix a single storage SRS and to perform all reprojection at the boundary, on ingestion.

The storage SRS is ETRS89 / UTM zone 32N (EPSG:25832). Three considerations converge on this choice. It is the official reference system of Baden-Württemberg, and the system in which the most authoritative regional data (the Gewässernetz, the LUBW networks, the cadastral layers) are natively published; adopting it minimizes the number of transformations needed at ingestion. It is also the system that INSPIRE recommends for environmental data in this part of Europe, so the storage choice aligns directly with the interoperability target rather than crossing it. And because it is a projected system in metric units, distance, area and buffer operations can be performed without first reprojecting on the fly.

The transformation policy follows. Every incoming dataset is transformed to EPSG:25832 once, at the point of ingestion, through a documented transformation path. DHDN data are transformed to ETRS89 by a published seven-parameter Helmert transformation; WGS84 data are transformed by the standard datum transformation for central Europe; WGS84/UTM imagery is transformed by direct geodetic transformation. The transformation parameters used for each record are recorded in `metadata.data_lineage`, so that the path from native source to stored geometry is reproducible. Reprojection to other systems for delivery (WGS84 geographic coordinates for web services, Web Mercator for tile-based visualization) is performed on the fly through PostGIS `ST_Transform`, so that the stored geometry is never overwritten and never degraded by successive reprojection. Rasters are reprojected at ingestion through GDAL `gdalwarp` with the resampling method chosen according to the data class: nearest neighbor for categorical layers such as land cover, bilinear for continuous surfaces such as elevation, and cubic for radiometric layers where smooth interpolation is appropriate. A residual datum-transformation error remains, typically of the order of decimeters for the DHDN-to-ETRS89 shift and of the sub-metre to roughly one-metre level for WGS84 sources without a regional transformation grid; this error is recorded in lineage rather than concealed, so that any downstream analysis sensitive to it can take it into account.

5.5 Temporal Design Strategy

The temporal half of the multi-scale problem is more demanding than the spatial half. The sources span about five orders of magnitude in cadence, from sub-hourly gauge readings to the six-yearly River Basin Management Plan cycle, and the design must permit these to be stored side by side, joined coherently, and queried by month, season, year or arbitrary interval without resorting to date arithmetic at query time.

The mechanism is a shared temporal backbone realized as the table `metadata.time_index`. The backbone is a pre-computed daily calendar for 2005–2025, populated once at initialization through `generate_series` over the date range, with each row carrying a surrogate primary key `time_id`, the date itself, and the derived fields `year`, `month`, `day`, `quarter`, `season`, `week`, `iso_week` and `day_of_year`, each indexed for query. Every observation and every raster dataset in the database hold a `time_id` foreign key into this backbone rather than an isolated date column. Analyses by month, season or year, which are the natural granularities of WFD reporting, are therefore expressed as joins on indexed integer keys, not as repeated extractions of date components from a timestamp, and are correspondingly fast.

The daily resolution of the backbone is the coarsest common unit that accommodates the data inventory: a Sentinel-2 acquisition occurs on a specific date, a manual reading is dated, an annual report is dated to its day of publication. Data that arrive at finer than daily granularity (hourly groundwater logger readings, sub-daily Pegelonline discharge) are accommodated through the additional

obs_timestamp column on insitu.observation that carries the precise instant of measurement, while the time_id link continues to bind the record to its day in the backbone. Data that arrive at coarser than daily granularity (annual reports, six-yearly management plans) are bound to a representative date on the backbone together with a validity interval, so that the question *"which plans were in force on the day this measurement was taken"* reduces to an interval containment join.

The valid-time and transaction-time columns introduced in Section 1.5.2 layer on top of the backbone rather than replace it. A corrected groundwater observation does not overwrite the original but is recorded as a new row whose valid time replaces that of the original and whose transaction time begins at the moment of correction. The resulting bitemporal record permits two distinct queries: *"what is the best current estimate of the groundwater level on 14 July 2018"* and *"what did we believe the groundwater level on 14 July 2018 to be, as of 1 January 2020"*. Monitoring agencies routinely need to answer both separately for audit and assessment-revision purposes, and an overwriting database cannot answer the second at all.

The indexing and partitioning strategy that makes such queries efficient (partitioning of insitu.observation and rs.rs_dataset by year, composite indexes on time_id together with station_id or dataset_id) is specified at the logical level here and reserved for physical realization in Lab Rotation II.

The same principle applies on the spatial axis. Because the resolution of every raster dataset is recorded as an explicit attribute on rs.rs_dataset, multi-scale queries can be expressed against it directly. A query may, for example, request the highest available resolution within a given area for a given date, with an automatic fallback to coarser products where finer ones are absent: a SELECT over rs.rs_dataset ordered by the resolution attribute, filtered by footprint intersection and acquisition date, returns the appropriate scene without committing the calling analysis to any specific sensor. This is the operational meaning of *multi-scale by design*: scale becomes a queryable property rather than a structural constraint.

The architecture set out in Section 1.5 is the outcome of a sequence of explicit choices, each made against the competing alternatives that the data inventory and the regulatory environment made available. This discussion reflects on the most consequential of those choices, qualifies the claims the design makes, situates it against both the established and the contemporary literature, and identifies the limitations that the work consciously accepts together with the open questions that Lab Rotation II will need to address.

The decision to hold raster payload as out-of-database file references registered through PostGIS Raster's `out_db` mechanism, rather than as fully in-database raster, is the choice with the largest operational consequences. A fully in-database approach would offer stronger referential integrity, a single point of backup and direct SQL access at the pixel level, and these are real advantages for smaller archives. They were judged decisively outweighed for a twenty-year multi-resolution archive spanning one-meter LiDAR to thirty-meter Landsat, where in-database storage of the payload would have produced a database of a size that compromises backup, replication and routine maintenance, and would also have removed the rasters from direct use by GDAL-based tooling external to the database. The hybrid arrangement adopted here keeps the database light and the rasters usable in place, at the cost of a looser coupling between catalogue and payload that ingestion and validation routines in Lab Rotation II must enforce explicitly.

Admitting raster into the same database bears on the integration principle itself, which requires qualification on the spatial axis. The principle that cross-source integration reduces to joins on shared keys rather than to ad hoc spatial or temporal reconciliation holds without reservation for point observations: a monitoring station occupies a single location, its containing spatial unit is determined once, and the relationship is stored as a foreign key that is thereafter a simple key match. A raster acquisition is different in kind, because a single scene footprint legitimately overlaps many spatial units, and the relationship between a scene and the units it covers is therefore intrinsically many-to-many rather than a single reference. The single `spatial_unit_id` carried on `rs.rs_dataset` should accordingly be read as a convenience denormalization recording the principal unit under which a scene is catalogued, not as the authoritative spatial relationship; the authoritative relationship is the footprint geometry. The qualification does not, however, reintroduce the cost the principle was meant to avoid. The scene-to-unit intersection is computed once, at ingestion, against geometry that is already in the single storage SRS and already spatially indexed, and is materialized into a scene–unit association, so that at query time the relationship is available as a key match in the same way as for point observations. What is reconciled once at ingestion is thus not only reference system and format but also the spatial membership of each raster scene, and the reprojection-free, intersection-free join at query time is preserved.

The choice of a single storage SRS in ETRS89/UTM zone 32N, rather than a multi-SRS schema with on-demand transformation, reflects a similar trade. Multi-SRS storage avoids any transformation at ingestion and is appropriate for systems whose use cases routinely require native-projection access. The water-monitoring use case envisaged here is the opposite: most analytical queries combine sources, and combining sources held in different reference systems would require transformation at query time on every operation, accumulating positional error and degrading performance. Reconciliation at the boundary, once, with the transformation parameters recorded in lineage, was therefore preferred over reconciliation at every query.

The long-format observation table absorbs variable cadence and admits new parameters without schema change, but it does so at the cost of larger table size and of more expensive aggregate queries than a wide table per parameter would have produced. For monitoring data in which dozens of parameters are measured across hundreds of stations with intermittent gaps, the wide alternative was judged unworkable: it would have committed the schema to a fixed parameter list at design time and would have wasted storage on null cells for every parameter not measured at a given station. The cost

of the long form is mitigated at the physical level through partitioning by year and through composite indexing on station, parameter and time, both of which are specified for Lab Rotation II.

One element of the temporal design presented tersely in Section 1.5 warrants fuller justification. The temporal backbone `metadata.time_index` is, in form, the conformed date dimension long established in data-warehouse practice, and it is adopted as such deliberately rather than offered as a novelty. Its principal justification is not the marginal speed of an integer key join over date-component extraction, which a modern PostgreSQL handles efficiently through expression indexes and generated columns in any case, but the provision of a single, shared and semantically rich set of temporal definitions, season, hydrological year, the six-year River Basin Management Plan cycle, ISO-week boundaries, computed once and referenced identically by every source, so that cross-source temporal alignment is definitional rather than reconstructed in each ingestion pipeline. At a few thousand rows for the entire study period the dimension is negligible in cost, and the benefit it secures is consistency of temporal semantics across otherwise incompatible sources rather than micro-optimization.

The bitemporal mechanism likewise deserves precise statement, since its correctness depends on details a schema diagram cannot show. A correction does not overwrite but appends: the logical identity of an observation, distinct from the surrogate primary key of any single physical row, is carried so that all versions of one measurement share an identity, while each version is a separate row bearing its own transaction-time interval. A correction inserts a new version whose transaction time opens at the moment of correction and closes the transaction interval of the superseded row; non-overlap of the intervals is enforced through range types and exclusion constraints. The current best estimate is then the version whose transaction interval contains the present and whose valid interval contains the queried instant, while the state as believed at a past moment is recovered by substituting that moment for the present in the transaction predicate. This is the application-time-plus-system-time model standardized in SQL:2011 (Kulkarni and Michels 2012), to which the design conforms.

The multi-scale character of the design merits a more precise statement than the term alone conveys. On the temporal axis the claim is met in full: sources whose cadence spans roughly five orders of magnitude are bound to a single backbone and queried at any granularity through it. On the spatial axis the delivered mechanism is multi-resolution holding and selection: resolution is an explicit, queryable attribute, and a query may select the finest available product or fall back to a coarser one, rather than scale-dependent cartographic generalization. Genuine generalization, the derivation of simplified vector geometries or raster overviews appropriate to a coarser scale of analysis, is a processing concern lying outside the conceptual and logical scope of this work; raster overview pyramids in particular are noted as an element of the physical realization in Lab Rotation II. The architecture makes scale a recorded and selectable property of every dataset, which is the sense in which it is multi-scale by design, but it does not itself perform generalization.

INSPIRE conformance was treated throughout as a structural commitment rather than as a wrapper. The alternative, common in practice, is to build a generic schema and to expose an INSPIRE-conformant view of it through a transformation layer. That alternative is pragmatically attractive but accumulates a debt: every change in the underlying schema requires a corresponding change in the transformation layer, and the resulting views are rarely a faithful realization of the INSPIRE model. By aligning the conceptual entities directly with the relevant INSPIRE data themes and by holding ISO 19115 metadata in a dedicated schema rather than as scattered columns, the design produces a database that is INSPIRE-aligned rather than one that exposes a conformant facade.

The claim of INSPIRE conformance should nonetheless be understood at the level at which it is made. What this work establishes is structural alignment: the conceptual classes are drawn from the relevant INSPIRE themes, and ISO 19115 metadata is held as a first-class part of the schema. Full conformance to the INSPIRE application schemas, the complete feature catalogue of a theme, its voidable attributes, association roles and GML encoding, is a property of the published network services and belongs to the implementation and service layer of Lab Rotation II. To make the structural claim concrete rather than asserted, a single worked correspondence is the appropriate next step:

base.monitoring_station maps onto the INSPIRE Environmental Monitoring Facilities feature type EnvironmentalMonitoringFacility, with its surrogate identifier extended to a namespaced inspireId, its point geometry, and its network affiliation expressed through the relevant code-list attributes; and a spatial unit of water-body type maps onto the corresponding Hydrography water-body feature. Such a crosswalk, carried for one feature type per theme, converts the alignment from a design intention into a demonstrated mapping, and is the form the alignment will take in the implementation specification of Lab Rotation II.

Placed against the existing literature, the design occupies a position that is recognizable but not duplicated. Horsburgh et al. (2009) describe an integrated system for publishing environmental observations whose Observations Data Model anticipates the long-format design adopted here for insitu.observation and is one of the antecedents of WaterML 2.0. Plana et al. (2019) address the related problem of water-quality data and emphasize structured metadata as the condition for reuse, an emphasis that this work shares and operationalizes through the dedicated metadata schema. What is added here is the joint treatment of in-situ, raster and documentary content under a common spatial-temporal backbone, with INSPIRE alignment as a structural feature and with bitemporality applied where the data are routinely revised. The contribution is in the integration of these elements, not in any one of them taken separately.

Two bodies of contemporary practice in earth-observation data management bear on the remote-sensing component and deserve explicit positioning. The first is the SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) specification, with which the rs schema converges closely: a row of rs.rs_dataset corresponds to a STAC Item, its footprint to the Item geometry, and the out-of-database file reference of rs.rs_tile to a STAC Asset. The catalogue is in this sense STAC-compatible in structure, and exposing it as a STAC-conformant catalogue is a natural extension that would reinforce rather than complicate the interoperability the design already targets. The second is the data-cube paradigm, exemplified by the Australian Geoscience Data Cube (Lewis et al. 2017), which organizes analysis-ready imagery as a dense, regularly gridded array. A data cube is well suited to analytics over harmonized raster but is a poor primary store for the problem addressed here, for three reasons: the archive is deliberately multi-resolution and multi-sensor, and forcing it into a single dense array would impose exactly the resampling and degradation the design avoids; the integration task is not raster alone but raster jointly with in-situ, vector and documentary content under INSPIRE, none of which a data cube models; and the bitemporal and lineage requirements central to this work fall outside the data-cube abstraction. The two approaches are therefore complementary rather than competing: the database serves as the integrating catalogue and the store of vector, observational and metadata content, while a data cube, fed from the rs catalogue, is the appropriate downstream layer for intensive raster analytics.

A clarification of the status of the performance statements made throughout Section 1.5 is finally in order. Where the design is described as supporting efficient or rapid queries, the claim is architectural rather than empirical: it follows from the structure of the data, not from measurement. The assertion that a catalogue query is answerable without touching the raster payload, for instance, rests on the difference in volume between a scene-level catalogue of kilobytes and a raster archive of terabytes, a difference that holds by construction. Statements about absolute response time, by contrast, are genuine empirical claims and are deliberately deferred: the logical schema specifies the indexing and partitioning on which such performance depends, but its measurement requires a populated database and is reserved for Lab Rotation II, where the schema is instantiated as executable data-definition statements and exercised against real holdings.

The limitations specified in Section 1.1.3 (the deferral of physical implementation to Lab Rotation II, the restriction to two- and two-and-a-half-dimensional geometry, the exclusion of real-time data and of licensed datasets) shape the work and frame the open questions that follow.

The open questions that remain are precisely those that Lab Rotation II is positioned to address. The empirical performance of the long-format observation table under multi-parameter queries needs to be measured against the alternatives. The fidelity of the out_db raster references under operational

backup and migration procedures needs to be tested, together with the integrity of the materialized scene–unit association under ingestion-time validation. The completeness of the mapping from native LUBW and Pegelonline code lists to the INSPIRE registry needs to be confirmed by full ingestion of the regional holdings, and the worked INSPIRE crosswalk extended from a single feature type per theme to the full set of themes the system carries. The responsiveness of the temporal backbone under realistic query patterns, including queries that traverse the bitemporal interval columns, needs to be characterized. And the STAC-compatibility of the rs catalogue, asserted structurally here, needs to be validated by exposing the catalogue as a conformant STAC endpoint. None of these questions can be answered at the design stage at which this work concludes; each becomes tractable once the schema is populated with real data, which is the work of the next lab rotation.

7 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

This report has set out the design of a multi-scale spatio-temporal database infrastructure for INSPIRE-compliant water monitoring in the Karlsruhe region, taking the design from the regulatory and theoretical background through the investigation of available data sources and the requirements they impose, to a conceptual and logical architecture that integrates them in a single PostGIS database. The contribution of the work is not in any one of its components but in the way they are assembled. Heterogeneous water-monitoring data from remote sensing, in-situ stations, vector networks and documentary sources are brought into a single database through a four-schema architecture (base, rs, insitu, metadata) whose schemas are bound by two common references, a spatial backbone in base and a temporal backbone in metadata.time_index. Spatial reference systems are reconciled once at ingestion against a single storage SRS, ETRS89/UTM zone 32N, with on-the-fly reprojection reserved for delivery; the temporal backbone permits joins across cadences spanning about five orders of magnitude; raster payload is held as out-of-database files referenced from a catalogue table, keeping the database light without sacrificing SQL-level discovery; and bitemporality is applied where the data are routinely revised, so that the history of belief is preserved alongside the history of fact. INSPIRE conformance is built into the structure of the schema rather than wrapped around it, and the resulting design is the binding specification under which the implementation of Lab Rotation II will proceed.

The transition to implementation has a defined sequence. The physical database will be instantiated on PostgreSQL with the PostGIS and PostGIS Raster extensions, the four schemas created, and the metadata.time_index table populated for the period 2005–2025. Code lists in insitu.parameter and the unit-type vocabularies in base.spatial_unit will be aligned with the INSPIRE registry and with the native vocabularies of the LUBW, Pegelonline and DWD networks. ETL pipelines will be developed for each source family, with particular attention to the DHDN-to-ETRS89 datum transformation for legacy national holdings, to the cloud, shadow and speckle preprocessing required for Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-1, and to the SLC-off handling and cross-sensor harmonization required for the Landsat archive. The catalogue-plus-reference raster strategy will be tested under realistic backup and migration procedures, and the responsiveness of the long-format observation table and the temporal backbone will be characterized under representative query loads. Once the schema is populated, the spatio-temporal queries that motivated the design, joining in-situ observations to remote-sensing acquisitions over WFD water bodies across the twenty-year window, will be exercised end to end as the empirical validation of the architecture. The questions left open at the close of this design phase (performance under multi-parameter queries, fidelity of the out_db raster references, completeness of the INSPIRE code-list mapping, behavior of the bitemporal interval queries) are precisely the questions that population of the database makes answerable, and Lab Rotation II is the place where they will be answered.

REFERENCES

- Allen, James F. 1983. “Maintaining Knowledge about Temporal Intervals.” *Communications of the ACM* 26(11):832–43. doi:10.1145/182.358434.
- Behmel, Sonja, Mathieu Damour, Ralf Ludwig, and M. J. Rodriguez. 2016. “Water Quality Monitoring Strategies—A Review and Future Perspectives.” *Science of the Total Environment* 571:1312–29.
- Craglia, Massimo, and Alessandro Annoni. 2007. “INSPIRE: An Innovative Approach to the Development of Spatial Data Infrastructures in Europe.” P. 93 in *Research and theory in advancing spatial data infrastructure concepts*. ESRI, Inc.
- European Commission. 2012. “Introduction to the EU Water Framework Directive: Common Implementation Strategy.” https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/water/water-framework-directive_en.
- European Parliament and Council. 2007. “Directive 2007/2/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 March 2007 Establishing an Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community (INSPIRE).”
- Hering, Daniel, Angel Borja, Jacob Carstensen, Laurence Carvalho, Mike Elliott, Christian K. Feld, Anna-Stiina Heiskanen, Richard K. Johnson, Jannicke Moe, and Didier Pont. 2010. “The European Water Framework Directive at the Age of 10: A Critical Review of the Achievements with Recommendations for the Future.” *Science of the Total Environment* 408(19):4007–19.
- Horsburgh, Jeffery S., David G. Tarboton, Michael Piasecki, David R. Maidment, Ilya Zaslavsky, David Valentine, and Thomas Whitenack. 2009. “An Integrated System for Publishing Environmental Observations Data.” *Environmental Modelling & Software* 24(8):879–88.
- Kulkarni, Krishna, and Jan-Eike Michels. 2012. “Temporal Features in SQL:2011.” *ACM SIGMOD Record* 41(3):34–43. doi:10.1145/2380776.2380786.
- Langran, Gail E. 1989. “A Review of Temporal Database Research and Its Use in GIS Applications.” *International Journal of Geographical Information Systems* 3(3):215–32. doi:10.1080/02693798908941509.
- Lewis, Adam, Simon Oliver, Leo Lymburner, Ben Evans, Lesley Wyborn, Norman Mueller, Gregory Raevksi, Jeremy Hooke, Rob Woodcock, and Joshua Sixsmith. 2017. “The Australian Geoscience Data Cube—Foundations and Lessons Learned.” *Remote Sensing of Environment* 202:276–92.
- McFeeters, S. K. 1996. “The Use of the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) in the Delineation of Open Water Features.” *International Journal of Remote Sensing* 17(7):1425–32. doi:10.1080/01431169608948714.
- Peuquet, Donna J. 1994. “It’s About Time: A Conceptual Framework for the Representation of Temporal Dynamics in Geographic Information Systems.” *Annals of the Association of American Geographers* 84(3):441–61. doi:10.1111/j.1467-8306.1994.tb01869.x.
- Plana, Queralt, Janelcy Alferes, Kevin Fuks, Tobias Kraft, Thibaud Maruéjols, Elena Torfs, and Peter A. Vanrolleghem. 2019. “Towards a Water Quality Database for Raw and Validated Data with Emphasis on Structured Metadata.” *Water Quality Research Journal* 54(1):1–9.
- Vörösmarty, Charles J., Peter B. McIntyre, Mark O. Gessner, David Dudgeon, Alexander Prusevich, Pamela Green, Stanley Glidden, Stuart E. Bunn, Caroline A. Sullivan, and C. Reidy Liermann.

2010. “Global Threats to Human Water Security and River Biodiversity.” *Nature* 467(7315):555–61.
- Voulvoulis, Nikolaos, Karl Dominic Arpon, and Theodoros Giakoumis. 2017. “The EU Water Framework Directive: From Great Expectations to Problems with Implementation.” *Science of the Total Environment* 575:358–66.
- Wilkinson, Mark D., Michel Dumontier, IJsbrand Jan Aalbersberg, Gabrielle Appleton, Myles Axton, Arie Baak, Niklas Blomberg, Jan Willem Boiten, Luiz Bonino Da Silva Santos, and Philip E. Bourne. 2016. “The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship: Comment.” *Scientific Data* 3:160018.
- Worboys, Michael F. 1994. “A Unified Model for Spatial and Temporal Information.” *The Computer Journal* 37(1):26–34. doi:10.1093/comjnl/37.1.26.
- Xu, Hanqiu. 2006. “Modification of Normalised Difference Water Index (NDWI) to Enhance Open Water Features in Remotely Sensed Imagery.” *International Journal of Remote Sensing* 27(14):3025–33. doi:10.1080/01431160600589179.